

A Crowdsourcing Approach for Identifying Potential Stereotypes in the Collected Data

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Abstract. Data generation through crowdsourcing has become a common practice for building or augmenting an Artificial Intelligence (AI) system. These systems often reflect the stereotypical behaviors expressed by humans through the reported data, which can be problematic, especially when dealing with sensitive tasks. One such task is the interpretation of images depicting people. In this work, we evaluate a crowdsourcing approach aimed at identifying the stereotypes conveyed in the collected annotations on people images. By including closed-ended, categorical responses as well as open-ended tags during the data collection phase, we can detect potentially harmful crowd behaviors. Our results suggest a means to assess descriptive tags, as to their alignment with stereotypical beliefs related to gender, age, and body weight. This study concludes with a discussion on how our analytical approach can be applied to pre-existing datasets with similar characteristics or to future knowledge being crowdsourced such as to audit for stereotypes.

Keywords: crowdsourcing · image tagging · stereotypes · bias · fairness.

1 Introduction

The goal of the European Commission (EC), as stated in the 2020 White Paper on AI is to promote the use of AI systems and the widespread sharing of AI systems, processes and resources (e.g., datasets, algorithms) ⁴. To this end, the EC has put forth a vision of trustworthy and fair AI systems, which must conform to human values⁵. Multiple approaches have been proposed for detecting and mitigating discrimination and fairness issues in AI systems such as auditing image search engines [20,12,17], detecting bias and stereotypical behaviors in image tagging services [1,18] or auditing input data using datasheets for datasets developed by the system stakeholders during the system development [8].

Stereotypical behaviors are inevitable when the AI system judges or interacts with people or artifacts (e.g., images, audio, texts) that depict or represent people; therefore, the issue is whether or not such behaviors constitute unfair social bias. It is even

⁴ [https : / / commission . europa . eu / publications / white-paper-artificial-intelligence-european-approach-excellence-and-trust_en](https://commission.europa.eu/publications/white-paper-artificial-intelligence-european-approach-excellence-and-trust_en)

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/ai-alliance-consultation.1.html>

more challenging when the training and input data of an AI system are generated by humans, who judge or interact with people or artifacts (e.g., images, audio, texts) that depict or represent people. Social stereotypes are transmitted and learned between people [13,25,26,10] and they can easily be propagated when someone is asked to judge/describe another person, without having enough information concerning that person [27]. Over time, social stereotypes detected in a dataset used to train an AI system may lead to a discriminatory decision or outcome. An example is the study of Matsangidou and Otterbacher [18] who audit the output of four image tagging services that generate tags to describe portrait images from the Chigago Face Database (CFD) [16], by compiling a dictionary of tags that are related to attractiveness (e.g., attractive, pretty, beautiful, cute, handsome). Among other results, they found that images of women were systematically more likely to receive “attractiveness” tags by the algorithms, as compared to images of men. They identified that these image tagging algorithms tend to perpetuate stereotypes related to gender.

Crowdsourcing, the process of recruiting humans to generate/augment data, is one means by which social stereotypes can easily be propagated to an AI system, through biased data. Crowdworkers, like most humans, have their own biases and express stereotypical behaviors that many times accompany the generated data, thus possibly biasing the final outcome of the AI system trained on those data. To handle these issues, several approaches have been proposed for mitigating bias in the collected data through the design of a crowdsourcing task. For instance, Draws et al. [5] composed a list of cognitive bias arising through crowdsourcing tasks, which they accompanied with insights on how to improve the task design for the generation of more reliable and trustworthy data sets. Hube et al. [9] proposed and reviewed three mitigation methods for a text annotation crowdsourcing task: i) Social projection, where the workers are asked to label a text according to what they believe the majority of workers would choose; ii) Awareness reminder, trying to make workers aware of the controversial and subjective nature of the task to influence their judgment when completing the task; iii) Personalized Nudges, giving personalized instructions to the workers according to the tendencies they exhibit in forming a judgment. The authors note that all three mitigation approaches reduce the total bias and average bias of workers with extreme opinions. Leung et al. [14] proposed another task design that reduces the number of choices that the crowdworkers have for their responses, which can reduce potential discrimination on the data generated by the responses. In a similar way, Kamar et al. [11] propose a method for automatically recognizing and correcting task-specific biases using probabilistic graphical models.

1.1 Our Approach

Most recent approaches emphasize the design of the crowdsourcing task for the generation of a less-biased dataset. In contrast, our approach aims at providing a way to evaluate the generated data through the structure of the crowdsourcing task for stereotypical behaviors, rather than “indiscriminately” mitigating potential biases arising from crowdsourcing, without first understanding the biases that arise and the reason for their existence. Our work presents a way for receiving indirect feedback on the data generated by crowdworkers, which allows us to explore the reasons for the generation of

systematic stereotypical beliefs in a dataset. In a sense, the crowdworkers act both as the “producer” of the data and the “evaluator” at the same time.

To better explore our approach, we consider the case of image recognition, via “tagging.” Various forms of image analysis and recognition (e.g., object recognition, captioning) have become popular in recent years, and have become an asset to researchers and developers, who need to add vision capabilities to a project, product or service. In most of the large datasets available for training such models (e.g., ImageNet, MSCOCO), crowdsourcing has played a key role in their creation and evaluation.

Inspired by this, we consider the example of image tagging via crowdsourcing and we ask the crowdworkers to provide tags for a set of highly standardized people images from the Chicago Face Database (CFD) [16]. These are passport-style images, with a neutral background, which allows us to capture tags directly relevant to the depicted person, thus avoiding background noise for this study. The crowdsourcing task, i.e., Human Intelligence Task (HIT) provided to the crowd is a collection of open and closed-form questions regarding the image. By collecting both categorical data on certain traits of the depicted person and a set of tags matching the depicted person, we aspire to both create a dataset useful for image tagging algorithms and audit the stereotypical beliefs of the crowdworkers collectively. Thus, we address the following research questions:

- RQ1: Can the inclusion of categorical values on certain person’s traits help in identifying potentially harmful stereotypes in an image tagging dataset?
- RQ2: Is it advantageous to include complementary open and closed-form questions in the same HIT for the identification of stereotypical behaviors?

To explore the above research questions, we examine the generated data set for any correlation between abstract i.e. attractiveness, trustworthiness, and concrete concepts i.e. weight, age, and gender that may propagate stereotypes such as: *Are younger people perceived as more attractive*, or *Are overweight people perceived as less attractive*?

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we present our methodology for collecting and processing the crowdsourced dataset. In Section 3, we present the analysis of the crowdworkers’ responses to both closed-form and open-form questions and the identified stereotypes from the dataset. In Section 4, we discuss our main findings with regard to the two research questions, we provide a discussion on how we could generalize our approach to other types of data and we discuss the limitations of this work. Finally, we provide some general remarks on this work and we discuss the possible future directions in Section 5.

2 Methodology

Data collection. We recruited US-based crowdworkers through the Clickworker platform⁶ and asked them to provide us with their observations (a.k.a., a description of the depicted person) on each of the 597 images of the Chicago Face Database (CFD) [16] data set. Images of CFD⁷ are highly standardized, with individuals depicted in the image self-reporting their gender and race. Out of the 597 images of the CFD, 109 depict

⁶ <https://www.clickworker.com/>

⁷ Sample images can be found at: <https://www.chicagofaces.org/>

Asian, 197 Black, 108 Latino/a and 183 White people. Additionally, gender is balanced per group.

After providing our crowdworkers a description of the task, we obtained their informed consent for participation; they were also explicitly informed of their right to leave the task at any time. We then asked them a series of questions regarding an image from the CFD data set.⁸ In particular, we asked them a control question concerning if they were able to see a person in the depicted image. After this question, we posed the following open-form question: "Fill in the 3 text fields below, providing a description of the depicted person with a maximum of 2 words." This question was followed by a set of closed-form questions. Crowdworkers were asked to respond, via a 1-7 Likert item (1 being the lowest, 7 the highest), as to how attractive they find the depicted person and how trustworthy they find them. Additionally, they were asked to gauge the weight of the person ([Underweight, Normal Weight, Overweight]), the person's race ([Asian, Black, Latino/a, White]), skin color ([Light, Medium, Dark]) and gender([Male, Female, Other]). Moreover, they were asked to report on the age of the person with an open-form question. Finally, workers were asked to complete a brief demographics questionnaire.

The crowdsourcing campaign sought out US-based participants, 18 years old or above to participate in the task. We asked for the participation of male and female crowdworkers in separate instances of the task, asking both genders to provide us with their opinion on all 597 images. Thus, we collected in total 1.194 responses from crowdworkers, each image receiving an annotation from both a male and a female crowdworker. Participants were rewarded with 0.6 euro per task and they took a median time of 4 minutes to complete the task.

Data set pre-processing. Crowdsourced data cannot be blindly trusted [7]. Thus we have pre-processed our dataset removing the answers received from crowdworkers who: 1) did not see a person in the depicted image, 2) reported that they were below 18 years of age, 3) reported that their gender was not the one specified during the task announcement, 4) provided us with gibberish tags. Hence, from the 1.194 responses we considered only 1.119.

Characteristics of the dataset. For the purpose of repeatability of our results and methodology, we provide here the main characteristics of our data set. Regarding the images depicting a person included in the dataset they are originally from the CFD data set showing individuals in a passport-like image, forward-facing the camera, wearing a grey t-shirt and having a neutral facial expression. This characteristic of the CFD has allowed us to observe the annotations of the crowdworkers as freely as possible from "attention biases" introduced to the tags due to the environment where the individual is portrayed. Open-form questions in the crowdsourcing task are pre-seeding the closed-form questions. This was done in an attempt to reduce the anchoring effect [5] that crowdworkers might have from introducing closed-form questions regarding the traits of the depicted person upfront.

⁸ Our research protocol has undergone ethical review and received approval by the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee.

3 Analysis and Results

We provide an analysis of the collected data looking into the responses of the crowdworkers to the open and closed-form questions. First, in Section 3.1, we consider the way crowdworkers reported on the more concrete characteristics that describe a person (i.e., gender, age and weight) and we compared them against the responses they provided for the abstract characteristics of a person (i.e., attractiveness and trustworthiness). Section 3.2 analyzes the frequencies with which certain tags were mentioned by the crowdworkers when a specific value was selected for the closed-form characteristics (both abstract and concrete).

Crowdworkers reported their perceived attractiveness and the trustworthiness of the depicted person using 7-point Likert items. For the purposes of this analysis, we collapsed the answers from the crowdworkers into three groups: (a) non-attractive/non-trustworthy (responses 1-3), (b) neutral (4), and (c) attractive/trustworthy (5-7).

The crowdworkers' reported values for age have also been divided into four groups: a) 15-24 years old, b) 25-34 years old, c) 35-44 years old, and d) 45+ years old.

3.1 General results of closed-form questions

Responses on each Characteristic. We first present the total number of crowdworkers' responses on each abstract and concrete characteristic for female and male images. In Table 1, we present the number of responses of the crowdworkers on each of the three attractiveness groups and on each of the three trustworthiness groups for female and male images respectively. We can observe that more females have been perceived as attractive, in contrast to males who have mostly been perceived as neutral or non-attractive. Regarding the trustworthiness of the people depicted in the images, most of the females and males have been perceived as neutral.

	Attractive	Neutral	Non-Attractive
Female Images	260	157	149
Male Images	168	191	194
	Trustworthy	Neutral	Non-Trustworthy
Female Images	230	260	76
Male Images	190	257	106

Table 1: Table with the responses for Attractiveness and Trustworthiness

In addition, as shown in Table 2, most of the people depicted in the images have been described to be of normal weight. Regarding age, we can observe that the majority of the people depicted in the images have been described to be in the age group 25-34.

Attractiveness v. Weight and Gender. To detect any association between the responses of crowdworkers on the abstract concept of attractiveness and the concrete concept of

	Underweight	Normal Weight	Overweight	
Female Images	18	454	94	
Male Images	22	470	61	
	15-24	25-34	35-44	45+
Female Images	110	329	100	27
Male Images	119	273	135	26

Table 2: Table with the responses for Weight and Age

weight, we examine the way crowdworkers perceive a person’s attractiveness, considering the description they provide of a person’s weight for both images depicting a male (see Fig. 1b) and images depicting a female (see Fig. 1a).

From an initial inspection of the results, it appears that crowdworkers who characterize a person as *overweight*, also tend to perceive the person as *non-attractive*, in both images depicting male and female subjects. Looking at the crowdworkers responses for female images, subjects depicted as having a *normal weight* also tend to be perceived as *attractive* or *neutral* rather than *non-attractive*. However, for male images, there is a very small difference between the number of responses provided to characterize a person as both *attractive* and of *normal weight*, and the number of responses provided to characterize a person as both as *non-attractive* and of *normal weight*. In other words, while we observe a uniform distribution over the value *normal weight* for the different values of *attractive* for the images depicting male subjects, this is not the case for the images depicting female subjects. On the contrary, more images depicting females marked as *attractive* receive also the *normal weight* value. Another observation we can make from Fig. 1b and Fig. 1a is that the *overweight* value is more frequently used for people marked as *non-attractive*, and it drops for *neutral* and *attractive* for both male and female subjects.

Attractiveness v. Age and Gender. We looked for an association between crowdworkers’ perceptions of the attractiveness of a person and the age of the person depicted in an image. As observed from Figure 1c, crowdworkers tend to perceive young females (around 15-24 or 25-34 years old) as being *attractive* more often than *non-attractive*, while they tend to perceive older females (over 45 years old) as *non-attractive*, and the females in the age group, 35-44 years old, as *neutral*. Based on these results, we observe that there is an association between the crowdworkers’ responses regarding the age of a female person and their perceived attractiveness. However, observing the results shown in Figure 1d, the stereotype that “younger people are more attractive than older people” has not been detected in responses concerning the male images. For males, we observe little difference between the number of responses that characterize a person as being *attractive* and in the younger (or older) age groups, and the number of responses that characterize a person as being *non-attractive* and in the younger (or older) age groups.

Trustworthiness v. Weight and Gender. We repeat the same analysis, this time looking into a possible relationship between the crowdworkers’ perceptions of a person’s trustworthiness, and their description of the person’s weight, for images depicting a male

Fig. 1: Perceived Attractiveness v. Age and Weight, by Gender.

(see Fig. 2b) and for images depicting a female (see Fig. 2a). As shown in both figures, the majority of crowdworkers perceive people depicted in both male and female images as *trustworthy* or *neutral* independently of their weight.

Trustworthiness v. Age and Gender. Figure 2c and Figure 2d depict the analysis considering possible associations between crowdworkers’ perceptions of a person’s trustworthiness and his or her age, for female and male images, respectively. For both female and male images, respectively, the largest percentage of responses describe a person, in any of the age groups, as *trustworthy* or *neutral* rather than *non-trustworthy*.

Trustworthiness v. Attractiveness and Gender. In considering the relationship between perceived trustworthiness, perceived attractiveness and gender, we detect that there is an association between attractiveness and trustworthiness. As shown both in figures, Figure 3a and Figure 3b, the majority of depicted people who have been perceived as being *attractive*, are also perceived as being *trustworthy*, while the majority of people who have been perceived as being *non-attractive* (or *neutral*) have also been perceived as being *non-trustworthy* or *neutral*.

3.2 Results from Open-form Questions

We now compare the open and closed-form responses provided by the crowdworkers. We consider the tags that were used by the crowdworkers when a certain value of the

Fig. 2: Perceived Trustworthiness v. Age and Weight, by Gender.

Fig. 3: Perceived Trustworthiness v. Perceived Attractiveness, by Gender.

closed-form questions was selected for both abstract and concrete characteristics of a person. In particular, we look at the percentage of the number of occurrences of a specific tag over the total number of tags provided for a specific value of the attractiveness, trustworthiness, age, gender, and weight characteristics (i.e., closed-form questions). Generated plots in this section depict tags with more than five occurrences, to remove the effects of any outliers.

Attractiveness Tags. Figure 4a shows the percentage of tag occurrences over the total number of tags given when the workers' closed-ended response indicates that the

depicted person is *attractive*. In contrast, Figure 4b shows the percentage of tag occurrences over the total number of tags given when the *non-attractive* value was selected by the crowdworkers.

Fig. 4: Open-ended (tags) v. Closed-ended responses on Attractiveness.

Looking at Fig. 4, we note similar behaviors from the crowdworkers, as we observed in the previous subsection regarding their closed-form responses. In particular, the “trustworthy” tag only appears in those used to describe people as *attractive*, providing even more evidence of the tendency to associate trustworthiness and attractiveness. Additionally, with respect to the association of a person’s attractiveness and weight, we observe that the “overweight” tag has been provided by workers to characterize people who have also been perceived as *non-attractive*. This adds to the evidence that overweight people are considered less attractive by the crowdworkers.

Another interesting finding is that crowdworkers use negative emotions such as “sad”, “mad” and “unhappy” more often when they perceive a person as *non-attractive*, while positive traits and characteristics i.e., “smart”, “intelligent”, “good” are used to describe people perceived as *attractive*.

Trustworthiness Tags. Figure 5a shows the percentage of occurrences of the tags given to describe a person perceived as being trustworthy, while Figure 5b shows the percentage of occurrences of the tags used to describe a person perceived as non-trustworthy. As shown in both figures, more concrete tags, such as demographic characteristics or those describing physical appearance, appeared more often to characterize people who have been perceived as *non-trustworthy*. In contrast, for people perceived as *trustworthy*, crowdworkers also provide more abstract characteristics i.e., “attractive”, “serious”, “smart”, and “calm”. Adding evidence to the conclusion that “people perceived as attractive are also perceived as trustworthy”, as shown in Figure 5a, attractiveness-related tags have been given to people who have been perceived as *trustworthy* i.e., “handsome”, “attractive”, “pretty” and “beautiful”.

We notice that tags like “young”, “adult”, and “middle-aged” described both people who have been perceived as *trustworthy* and as *untrustworthy*. This observation

Fig. 5: Open-ended (tags) v. Closed-ended responses on Trustworthiness.

supports the one extracted above from the closed-form questions, that crowdworkers perceive the depicted subjects as trustworthy or not, independently of their age. Finally, another interesting finding is that the tag “female” has been given more often to people who have been perceived as *trustworthy*, whereas “male” has been given more often to people who have been perceived as *non-trustworthy*.

4 Discussion and Limitations

4.1 Crowdworkers as data “evaluators”

Considering the responses to both the open and closed-form questions, we observed that crowdworkers’ answers tend to reflect “established” stereotypical beliefs and opinions, which are prevalent in society. In summary, we found evidence that the following stereotypes are reflected in the collected data: overweight people are unattractive [23,22], women are (or should be) attractive [3], and beautiful people are also “good” ([4] or, more specifically, more trustworthy [24].

In particular, the crowdworkers in our study perceived people that they judged as *overweight* more often as *non-attractive* compared to *neutral* and *attractive*. Additionally, female subjects have been considered more *attractive* than male subjects. These observations concur with stereotypical beliefs related to weight and attractiveness [22] as well as to gender and attractiveness [3]. On the other hand, we didn’t observe any definitive connection between age and attractiveness in the crowdworkers answers. Finally, comparing the responses received from the crowdworkers on the closed-form questions regarding the abstract traits of a person (i.e., attractiveness and trustworthiness), we have seen that independently of the gender of the depicted person, depicted subjects being marked as *non-trustworthy* were more frequently marked as being *non-attractive* and vice-versa. A similar conclusion was observed in the open-form questions with tags describing the attractiveness of a subject matching the value of trustworthiness in the closed-form question. This behavior of the crowdworkers adheres with the stereotype that more attractive people are regarded as more good [4] and in extension more

trustworthy. Thus, it is evident that crowdworkers have stereotypical opinions which are expressed in the generated data.

Hence, the above observations provide us with an *affirmative answer to RQ1*. Using closed-form questions that require the workers to directly express an opinion on certain traits of a person (i.e., trustworthy and attractive) in combination with questions that regard the general perception of a person in a concrete manner (i.e., gender, age, weight), can provide useful insights on the stereotypical beliefs that influence their work.

We have observed that the majority of the stereotypical beliefs expressed by the crowdworkers are reflected through the closed-form questions and confirmed from the open-form questions which are analyzed considering the responses of the crowdworkers regarding the closed-form questions. Thus, *in response to RQ2, it is advantageous to include complementary open and closed-form questions in the same HIT*. First of all, in image tagging HITs, open-form questions are desirable many times; thus, closed-form questions are desirable for recognizing stereotypical beliefs. Secondly, we have noticed that certain behaviors – such as attributing tags of “smart”, “serious” and “calm” to subjects marked as *trustworthy*, and tags like “smart”, “intelligent” and “good” to subjects marked as *attractive*, while subjects marked as *non-attractive* received tags as “sad”, “mad”, and “unhappy” – could only be noticed through the use of both types of questions. It is important to note that training data reflecting an association between a depicted subject’s emotional state and how attractive that person is, could lead to undesirable behaviors for a machine learning algorithm, e.g., systematically labeling humans that showed negative emotions as being non-attractive. Thus, it appears that this approach could potentially aid in “identifying” such behaviors in the dataset that are not easy to capture otherwise.

4.2 Generalizing the approach

Having received a positive answer to both research questions, for the example of crowd-sourced image tag generation for people images, we would like to highlight the main characteristics of our approach that allowed us to identify these stereotypical behaviors. This will allow us to provide some insides into how this approach could be generalized to other types of images and crowdsourced data.

Crowdsourced data. Our approach focused on crowdsourced data for image tag generation. We accompanied the HIT by asking crowdworkers to provide tags for a person depicted in images, with closed-form questions with the goal to identify the following main elements of the crowdworker’s perception of the depicted person: (a) demographic characteristics (i.e., more concrete characteristics), (b) personality traits (i.e., more abstract characteristics). Demographic characteristics are necessary to establish the cworker’s perception when annotating an image beyond the ground truth. In other words, when studying worker behavior, it is more helpful to know what gender/age the worker perceives the depicted person as having, rather than the ground truth. On the other hand, personality traits are valuable as we saw in identifying more “subtle” stereotypical behaviors. Pre-existing datasets with similar characteristics to the ones we describe above could be audited for systematic stereotypical beliefs. Moreover, when

generating new data that describe an image content with the aid of the crowd, an approach of using both open and closed-form questions can be applied. It is important though that the open questions precede the closed-form questions to avoid confirmation bias [5].

Furthermore, although we have looked into the paradigm of image tagging, this approach could be applicable to other types of crowdsourcing tasks that could benefit from an audit of the stereotypical beliefs of crowdworkers in a measurable way (i.e., through closed-form questions). A prime example is that of subjective tasks where the crowdworkers are asked to perform content moderation or sentiment analysis [6] and have a way to capture their perception in a measurable way.

Stereotype identification. To draw relevant conclusions on the existence of systematic stereotypical behaviors from the crowdworkers, the open and closed-form questions must be complementary. In other words, closed-form questions must establish in a countable manner, certain beliefs of the crowdworkers, so as to be compared against more qualitative responses. Identification of the stereotypes could be in a similar manner as in our analysis.

4.3 Limitations

Although we collected the crowdworkers’ responses on the race and skin color of the depicted person, we decided not to use these “concrete” characteristics in the analysis we have performed. Results on these two answers need a more thorough investigation, since many of the CFD images appear to depict multiracial subject, despite that the dataset provides a discrete race label. Thus, it is not easy to appropriately capture the perception of crowdworkers into meaningful results.

The analysis regarding the relationship of the tags with the concrete and abstract characteristics of the depicted person could be even more elaborated with the use of an appropriate dictionary that would categorize the tags, as in [2]. The dictionary presented in [2] could potentially be applied to this work, but to our understanding the categorization of the tags would need to be updated to better capture how crowdworkers judge a person. For example, the abstract characteristic categories should expand to include the education of a person, socioeconomic status and other social attributes, while the emotions category should expand to include both positive and negative emotions.

4.4 Stakeholder upskilling

The latest developments in Generative AI have shown the clear potential of the technology, and AI in general, in the efficient creation of content. However, what is less clear is the creation of appropriate and trustworthy datasets for developing and evaluating these AI models [15]. Bias detection and mitigation are crucial components when developing fair and explainable algorithmic systems, particularly in applications that involve social aspects, such as healthcare and education. A survey by Orphanou et al. [19] underscores the need to look into the system’s components as well as the perspective of the stakeholders when auditing and mitigating bias. In this work, we focused on the evaluation of the produced datasets via crowdsourcing, providing an approach for identifying

stereotypical beliefs of the crowdworkers. To this respect, as mentioned in Section 4.2 requesters of the crowdsourcing task must adapt their task in such a way as to be able to compare the more quantitative responses to the qualitative ones. Additionally, we have briefly discussed the characteristics that an existing crowdsourced dataset must have in order to be audited under the approach we have described.

The major stakeholders in the case of generating and using datasets for the creation and evaluation of AI models are usually software developers, researchers and industry practitioners. It is crucial to educate stakeholders on both the ramifications of training AI models with biased datasets, and the consequences of relying on datasets generated exclusively by a specific demographic group of crowdworkers. This education is essential for helping requesters comprehend the importance of evaluating the generated dataset and for establishing appropriate mechanisms to conduct such evaluations. Perikleous et al. [21] presented a tool for raising the stakeholders' awareness showing the behavior of four biometric tasks trained on crowdsourced image annotations.

On the other hand, another stakeholder in this equation are the users of an AI model, thus, crowdworkers also fall under this category. Raising awareness on the crowdworkers' side can be also beneficial. Although tools like the one mentioned above [21] can be of great help in educating crowdworkers a-priori, it is usually the case that they will significantly impact the cost of the crowdsourcing task. Given the current operational structure of commercial crowdsourcing platforms, it would be more advantageous if awareness on such issues were disseminated directly through the platform environment, integrated into a qualification scheme for crowdworkers.

5 Conclusions

This work presents a crowdsourcing approach for identifying stereotypical beliefs of the crowdworkers through the use of open and closed-form questions in the crowdsourcing task. Considering the paradigm of image recognition via tagging, a crowdsourcing task is designed for collecting tags from the crowdworkers on the CFD images together with the crowdworkers' perception on certain closed-form questions. Closed-form questions capture the perception of the crowdworkers both on concrete (i.e., gender, age, weight) as well as abstract features (i.e., attractiveness and trustworthiness). Analysis of the collected responses found evidence that crowdworkers considered women to be attractive, overweight people to be unattractive and attractive people to be more trustworthy and these beliefs were reflected on the tags provided by the crowdworkers. This work showed that not only crowdworkers' beliefs aligned with known social stereotypes but also that the use of both open and closed-form questions in combination can expose systematic behaviors of the crowdworkers that can be missed otherwise.

In the future, we aim at constructing a dictionary that would aid the identification of stereotypes in tags in line with our approach. Additionally, we aspire to apply this approach to other types of crowdsourcing tasks, such as text annotation and sentiment analysis. Finally, we would like to extend our current experiments to understand the degree to which the crowdworkers' demographics (e.g., their reported gender, race and/or nationality) correlate to the stereotypical beliefs observed in the generated data.

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